

Million of Erasmus Grants

Prototype based on Proof of
Concept

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This report sums up the work done in developing a prototype of the online application described in the report “MEGA Project: Blueprint and Proof of Concept design”. The aim has been to make a prototype that (a) illustrate a solution for students, (b) shows how institutions can use the online application to manage Erasmus+ grant payments, and (c) show that the APIs described in the report can be used to communicate with external systems. Mock-up of a financial payment system has been made to illustrate the use of some of these APIs. The communication between the Online application and the Payment system can be illustrated as shown below.

To avoid working with real user data all the data in the prototype are made up. Because of this and because authentication is considered outside the scope of this prototype there are no user login in the application.

The pages in the prototype are only available in English language, and all amounts are given in Euro (€).

To reduce development time OutSystems [1], the low code platform licensed to Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, has been used.

[1] <https://www.outsystems.com>

2. The prototype

The functions of the application are illustrated in the use case diagram shown in Figure 1. It shows the four main user roles in the application – the student, the mobility manager, the financial manager and the administrator of the application, and the different tasks each role can perform in the application.

Each of the different tasks (use cases) are described in more detail below, but first a few words about the data in the application and the APIs.

Figure 1: Use case diagram of Proof of Concept

3. The data model

All data shown and manipulated in the application are stored in a database. The entities and their relation are shown in Figure 2. Some of these entities holds values not possible to change in the prototype: the Status entity, the Currency entity, and the Mobility Manager entity.

The Status entity contains all the different statuses a payment can hold during its lifetime in the application. In the prototype these statuses are:

- Pending validation
- Validated
- Queued for payment
- Initiated
- Cancelled
- Failed
- Payment made

The Currency entity contains the code of some selected currencies according to ISO 4217 [1].

The Mobility Manager entity contains made up names of mobility managers in the prototype.

All other entities in the database will hold values depending on actions taken in the application.

This will be discussed in further details in later chapters.

Figure 2: Database model in Proof of Concept

In addition to the entities shown in the Figure 2 a special entity containing the settings of the application is made. The attributes are IsFinancialValidation Req (Boolean) and DayOfMonth (Integer). The values of these attributes can be changed by the administrator and are discussed in later chapters.

[1] <https://www.iso.org/iso-4217-currency-codes.html>

4. The API endpoints

The API endpoints in the application enables the data exchange between external systems (i.e. a beneficial module and a payment systems) and the application. In the prototype, the following three API endpoints are made:

1. **payment_requests**
2. **get_queued_payments**
3. **set_payment_status**

Payment Requests endpoint

Endpoint: /payment_requests
Method: POST
Parameters: none
Request body: JSON array, for instance:

```
[  
{  
  "StudentId": "",  
  "name": "",  
  "address": "",  
  "BankAccount": "",  
  "Amount": 0.1,  
}  
]
```

The payment_requests endpoint can be used to add students and their payment requests to the application.

Get Queued Payments endpoint

Endpoint: /get_queued_payments

Method: GET

Parameters: none

Response: JSON array, for instance:

```
[
  {
    "StudentId": "",
    "name": "",
    "address": "",
    "BankAccount": "",
    "Amount": 0.1,
    "academicyear": "",
    "transaction_id": ""
  }
]
```

The `get_queued_payments` endpoint can be used to get data about payments queued for payment. The Financial System mock-up consumes this endpoint to get all new payments queued for payment. The `transaction_id` parameter identifies the payment uniquely in the application.

Set Payment Status endpoint

Endpoint: /set_payment_status

Method: POST

Parameters: none

Request body: JSON, for instance:

```
{
  "transaction_id": "",
  "status": "",
  "reason": ""
}
```

The `set_payment_status` endpoint can be used to update the status of a given payment, identified by the `transaction_id` parameter. The Financial System mock-up uses the same statuses as the one in the application prototype. In a real Financial System this will probably not be the case. Some sort of translation of the status between the online application and the Financial System must be expected so that correct statuses are saved in the database.

Final remark on API endpoints

Both the `get_queued_payments` endpoint and the `set_payment_status` endpoint are consumed by the Financial System mock-up. In a real-world scenario, it could be difficult to get a Financial System to perform this task. In that case some sort of proxy service must be introduced in the workflow [1].

[1]At The Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, a similar workflow exists, and in the communication with the Financial System a mix of API and RPA is used.

5. Student access

The first time a student logs in to the application the profile page to the student will be shown. Here the student can correct their own information and confirm that the information is correct. The profile page will continue to be shown automatically when the student logs in on the application as long as the correct information checkbox is not selected.

For the student it is important that the Bank Account field has a valid value. If this value is empty no actions can be done on the student's payments by the Mobility Manager.

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for 'MEGAstudent'. The page is titled 'Profile'. It contains a form with the following elements:

- Name:** A text input field containing 'Kristoffer Robin'.
- Address:** An empty text input field.
- Bank Account:** An empty text input field.
- This information is correct:** A checkbox that is currently unchecked.
- Buttons:** A 'Close' button (white with blue border) and a 'Save' button (solid blue).

Figure 3: Student profile page as shown on a smartphone

When the Profile page is closed, either by selecting the Close or the Save button, the status page will be opened. Here the student can follow the status of their grant payments (see Figure 4). Notice that the final payment contains information about when the final payment will be paid (see Manage Erasmus+ projects on page 13 for information about how this text is created).

Figure 4: Student Status page as shown on a smartphone

In Figure 4 the normal steps of payments are shown. The different exception statuses for a payment; cancelled and failed are shown in Figure 5. Notice that the reason of cancellation and failure is shown to the student, which makes it possible for the student to react and maybe fix the cause for the exception.

Figure 5 Exception statuses as shown to the student

5. Mobility manager access

The main page for Mobility Managers is shown in Figure 6.

As default, after login as a Mobility Manager, all the payments with status set to Pending validation (marked 1 in Figure 6) and assigned to this Mobility Manager are shown. Both payment status and academic year can easily be changed in dropdowns (1 and 2 in Figure 6). And if a mobility manager wants to check the status of payments assigned to other managers or payments not assigned at all the switch just over the table can be used (4 in Figure 6).

When performing tasks, such as cancel or release payment, the payments in question must be selected first. This is done by selecting all or individual payments from the list (3 in Figure 6). The different tasks that can be performed after one or more payments have been selected by a Mobility Manager are:

Cancel Payment: Cancel all the selected payments. Before this task can be completed a reason for the cancellation must be given. After completion the status of the selected payments are changed to Cancelled.

Release Payment: All the selected payments are released for the next progression stage. If a Financial Manager is in the loop the next status will be Validated, but if no Financial Manager is needed the next status will be Queued for payment.

Deactivate student: Deactivates the students identified by the selected payments. All further processing of payments belonging to a deactivated student is not possible.

Restart process: Restarts the payment process of all selected payments. Only payments with status Failed or Cancelled can be restarted. A list of these payments will be shown if Payment Status (1) is set accordingly.

Take ownership: Assigns all the selected payments to the logged in Mobility Manager. The same effect can be achieved by cancelling or releasing the same payments.

Figure 6: Main page for Mobility Managers

At any time, an export to an Excel file can be made. This is done by clicking the small Excel icon just above the upper right corner of the table (5 in Figure 6). The file will contain the same columns as in the table, and the content of the file will be all the payments currently in view.

By clicking the name of a student in a list shown in the main page for Mobility Managers, a new page with detailed information about the student and her payments will be shown (see Figure 7: Page for student and payments details). In this new page the Mobility Manager can update both the information about the student (name, address and bank account) and the amount to be paid for payments where the status is set to Pending validation or Validated.

MEGA MEGAPoC

Details for student: Karen Lynch

Address:

Bank Account: T20X030 020 328 064 018 56 058 38

Name: Karen Lynch

Save Cancel

Initial payment

907,9 Save Do not save

Final payment

100,1

Status	Updated	Reason
Pending validation	18/06/2024	

Close

Figure 7: Page for student and payments details

5. Financial manager access

The main page for Financial Managers is shown in Figure 8.

As default, after login as a Financial Manager, all the payments with status set to Validated (marked 1 in Figure 8) are shown. Both payment status and academic year can easily be changed in dropdowns (1 and 2 in Figure 8).

When performing tasks, such as cancel or release payment, the payments in question must be selected first. This is done by selecting all or individual payments from the list (3 in Figure 8). The different tasks that can be performed after one or more payments have been selected by a Financial Manager are:

Cancel Payment: Cancel all the selected payments. Before this task can be completed a reason for the cancellation must be given. After completion the status of the selected payments are changed to Cancelled.

Release Payment: All the selected payments are released for the next progression stage, i.e. the status is set to Queued for payment.

By clicking the name of a student in a list shown in the main page for Financial Managers, a new page with detailed information about the student and her payments will be shown. This is the same page as the Mobility Manager will get (see Figure 7: Page for student and payments details) and the available actions are the same.

The screenshot displays the 'Payment Financial Manager Interface' with a search bar and a table of payment records. The table has columns for Select, Academic Year, Student, Payment, Amount, Payment Status, Date, Comments, and Project. Two rows of data are visible, both with a 'validated' status. Below the table, there are two buttons: 'Cancel Payment' and 'Release Payment'.

Select	Academic Year	Student	Payment	Amount	Payment Status	Date	Comments	Project
<input type="checkbox"/>	2023/2024	Augustine Batz	Final	€261.60	validated	10.07.2024		KA131 2023
<input type="checkbox"/>	2023/2024	Michele Feest	Initial	€1,207.00	validated	23.07.2024		Erasmus+ KA131_Students

Figure 8: Main page for Financial Managers

5. Administrator access

Figure 9 Main page for Web Application Administrators

When a Web Application Administrator logs in, the main page is shown (see Figure 9). The page is divided into four different parts: Application Parameter settings, Data Import, Manage Erasmus+ projects and Manage Payments. The tasks an administrator can perform in these parts are described below.

Change Application Settings

In this part of the page the administrator can change settings that affects the behaviour of the application (see Figure 10):

• **Is Financial Validation Required.** Tick the checkbox that indicates whether financial validation is required or not. If checked the role of a Financial Manager is available, and all payments must be validated by a person holding this role before it is queued for payment. If this checkbox is not checked the role of a Financial Manager is not available and all payments validated by a Mobility Manager will automatically be queued for payment.

• **Day of Month the payment will be executed.** Holds a single numeric value between 0 and 28. If no value is given or if the value is set to zero the payment will be executed as soon as possible. All other legal values indicate which day of the month the payment will be executed.

Figure 10 Section for Application Parameter Settings

Import data

In this part of the page the administrator can import student data and payment amounts (see Figure 11). The prototype only reads xlsx files exported from the Beneficiary Module.

Figure 11 Section for data import

When importing a new file from the Beneficiary Module the following actions and logic are applied for each student listed:

1. Check the value in the column Draft Mobility activity. Only rows where the value in this column is set to 'NO' will be processed further.
2. Check if the Erasmus+ project is already registered in the application. For this check the value in the column Grant Agreement No. is used. If the project is not registered a new project is created in the application, and the value of the field Initial Payment Percentage is set to 100 (more on this in Manage Erasmus+ projects below).
3. Check if the student is already registered in the application. For this check the value in the column Mobility activity ID[1] is used. If the student is not registered a new student is created in the application with name, email, and total grant amount read from the imported file. For each student created this way new payments for this student is also created; one payment if the Initial Payment Percentage is set to 100 and two payments (initial and final) if it's not.

If, on the other side, the student is already registered a set of new checks are applied:

- a. If the total grant amount read from the imported file is the same as the amount already saved in the application no further actions are taken.
- b. If the amount differs the logic is as follows:
 - i. Find the first payment where the status is either Pending validation or Validated.
 - ii. Adjust the amount in the payment(-s) to reflect the changed value of the total grant amount.
 - iii. If no payments are found that meet the criterion a new payment is created for the student in question.
 - iv. Notice that a change in the total grant amount can lead to a payment with a negative value.

[1] An alternative solution would be to use the column European student identifier to identify the student. This is an identifier that would identify the same student across different projects. But since this column has been empty in the files tested with during development the column Mobility activity ID has been used instead.

Manage Erasmus+ projects

In this part of the page all existing projects are shown. The administrator can either edit existing Erasmus+ projects or add new ones (see Figure 12). Below the focus will be on editing existing projects.

The screenshot displays the 'Manage Erasmus+ projects' interface. It features two main project cards side-by-side. The left card is titled 'Brussels 2024' and the right card is titled 'Erasmus+ ICM 2024'. Each card contains the following fields and controls:

- Grant Agreement No:** A text input field containing the ID '2024-1-NO01-KA131-HED-000206255' for Brussels 2024 and '2024-1-NO01-KA131-HED-000206201' for Erasmus+ ICM 2024.
- Initial Payment Percentage:** A horizontal slider control. For Brussels 2024, the slider is set to 70. For Erasmus+ ICM 2024, the slider is set to 80. The scale ranges from 0 to 100 in increments of 10.
- Exchange Currency:** A text input field.
- Exchange Rate:** A text input field.
- Explain when final payment will be paid:** A text area. For Brussels 2024, the text is 'When you have completed COS'. For Erasmus+ ICM 2024, the text is 'Will be paid when ...'.
- Edit Project:** A button located at the bottom of each card.

At the bottom right of the interface, there is a blue button labeled 'Add new project'.

Figure 12 Section for managing Erasmus+ projects

By clicking the Edit Project button an edit page will be shown (see Figure 13). When an Erasmus+ project is created by import from Beneficiary Module the name of the project will be the same as the Grant Agreement No. The Grant Agreement No is not possible to edit because it identifies the project in Beneficiary Module.

Three values are possible to alter in the edit project page. First the name of the project. This is the name that will be shown as the header of each Erasmus+ project in the overview of all projects (see Figure 12). Second the Initial Payment Percentage. If set to 100 the total grant will be issued in one payment. For all other values the grant will be split in two payments accordingly: the initial payment and the final payment. If the value is changed it will affect the amount of the payments due from the project. The main rule is that only payments to a student where the status of the initial payment to that student is either Pending validation or Validated will be changed. For each student the logic is as follows:

- 1.If the value is changed from 100 to a lower value, the total amount to the student will be split in two payments; initial and final as described above.
- 2.If the old and the new value both are lower than 100 the amount of all affected payments are changed accordingly.
- 3.If the value is changed to 100 the amount of the initial payment is set to the total grant amount, and the final payment is deleted.

Third the explanation of when the final payment will be paid. This information will be shown on the final payment of the student.

Edit project

Grant Agreement No.
2024-1-NO01-KA131-HED-000206255

Name of Project
Brussels 2024

Initial Payment Percentage
70

Exchange Currency
[Empty field]

Exchange Rate
[Empty field]

Explain when final payment will be paid
When you have completed COS

Save **Cancel**

Figure 13 The page for editing a project

Assign students to Mobility Managers

In this part of the page the administrator can assign students to Mobility Managers (see Figure 14). Projects that are connected to both a Erasmus+ project and a mobility manger will automatically disappear from the list of manageable payments.

Assign students to Mobility Managers ^

Select	Student	Amount	Paid from project	Mobility Manager
<input type="checkbox"/>	Aida Schuster	€1 436.00	Brussels 2024	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Logan Wunsch	€1 280.00	Erasmus+ ICM 2024	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Juston Ward	€1 381.00	Brussels 2024	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Wlfferd Casper	€1 316.00	Erasmus+ ICM 2024	

1 to 4 of 4 items

Add to manager

Figure 14 Section for managing payments

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